

Exploring Yoga's Potential in Male Infertility Management: Review Paper

Dr. Vadde Venkata Karthik¹, BNYS, MD (Clinical Yoga) Scholar, Dr. Subhashini M A², BNYS, MD (Clinical Yoga) Scholar, Dr. Aditi Giridharan, BNYS, MD (Clinical Naturopathy) Scholar

^{1&3} SDM College of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences, Ujire.

² International Institute of Yoga & Naturopathy Medical Sciences, Chengalpattu

Introduction:

Infertility is commonly described as the failure of a couple to achieve conception after engaging in frequent unprotected sexual intercourse for a period of one year or more (1). Male infertility, on the other hand, is characterized by a man's inability to impregnate a fertile female partner, persisting for at least one year of unprotected intercourse. Men are solely accountable for approximately 20% of infertility cases and contribute to an additional 30% to 40% (2). As both male and female factors often coincide in infertility cases, it's crucial to assess and manage both partners together. Male-related issues play a substantial role in around 50% of infertility instances. Various factors contribute to male infertility, ranging from reversible to irreversible conditions. Additionally, factors such as age, medication history, surgeries, exposure to toxins, genetic predispositions, and systemic illnesses can affect both partners (3). The primary goal of evaluating male infertility is to pinpoint contributing factors, provide reversible treatments, assess eligibility for assisted reproductive techniques (ART), and offer guidance for irreversible conditions. Occasionally, male infertility may signal underlying medical concerns, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive assessments to detect and address any significant health issues (4).

Etiology:

Male infertility can stem from various causes, categorized by their general underlying reasons. These encompass endocrine disorders, predominantly hypogonadism, accounting for approximately 2% to 5% of cases. Sperm transport disorders, like vasectomy, contribute around 5% of cases. Primary testicular defects, characterized by abnormal sperm parameters without identifiable causes, make up the majority, estimated at 65% to 80%. Additionally, there are cases classified as idiopathic, where males exhibit normal sperm and semen parameters, accounting for approximately 10% to 20% of instances (5).

Epidemiology:

The precise prevalence of male infertility remains uncertain due to several factors. Since male infertility is not a disease that requires reporting, its prevalence is not accurately documented. Additionally, because male infertility treatments are typically paid for privately, they are not captured in medical insurance statistics. Moreover, the treatment of male infertility commonly occurs in outpatient settings, and this data is typically not included in extensive clinical databases (5).

While baseline semen quality and sperm functional parameters among fertile Indian men have been documented, there is limited data on the declining sperm count in Indian males (6). A study conducted in South India over 13 years revealed a decline in sperm count by 30.31%, with reductions of 22.92% in sperm motility and 51.25% in sperm morphology (7). Notably, the increased incidence of sperm morphological abnormalities, coupled with low sperm count, suggests qualitative impairments in spermatogenesis and potentially in Sertoli cells (8). Decreased semen quality plays a significant role in male infertility. The exact reason for the decline in semen quality is not clear, but it may be due to environmental, nutritional, socioeconomic or other unknown causes (9–12).

COVID-19 seems to lead to decreased fertility and even infertility in certain males who have recovered, particularly those who experienced severe infections. The virus affects the testes through direct cellular infection, cytokine storms, and the effects of antiviral and immunological treatments. Further research is necessary to fully understand the mechanisms of damage and potential treatments tailored to COVID-19-related infertility (13).

Pathophysiology:

Sperm quality tends to decrease with advancing paternal age, a decline that can be observed from around the age of 35. This decline may contribute to cases of male infertility, recurrent miscarriages, and the occurrence of autosomal dominant single-gene disorders in offspring. Even in cases where routine semen parameters appear normal, abnormalities in the male genome, such as damaged sperm DNA, can indicate subfertility. DNA integrity testing is now accessible in clinical settings, with results potentially predicting reproductive outcomes. Oxidative stress has been linked to both sperm quality and infertility (14).

Fig: Relationship of the primary pathologies of the male reproductive system, oxidative stress and infertility (15)

The generation of ROS can be exacerbated by environmental, infectious, and lifestyle etiologies (16–18). For example, exposure to cigarette smoke generates high levels of OS, directly increasing seminal leukocyte concentrations and seminal ROS generation, and decreasing seminal levels of the antioxidant enzyme superoxide dismutase (SOD). Smoking decreases concentrations of the seminal plasma antioxidants thereby reducing the oxidant scavenging capacity of the spermatozoa and seminal fluid (19). Oxidative stress can be measured using direct and indirect assays. Direct assays measure the net oxidative sum of the balance between ROS production and intra- and extracellular antioxidants that scavenge ROS. The most used direct assay measures malondialdehyde, one of the final products of sperm cell

membrane lipid peroxidation. Quantification of sperm DNA damage has also been used as a direct assay of intracellular ROS-induced oxidant injury (20).

Yoga for Male Infertility

Recent attention has been directed towards therapeutic strategies for managing oxidative stress (OS) in male infertility. 80.4% of patients reported using at least one integrative medicine modality to treat infertility (Acupuncture: 38.5%, Yoga: 27.6%, Massage: 25.8%, Meditation: 16.7%, and Herbal supplements: 18.5%). Diet therapy was the most frequently utilized modality (74.0%) followed by body therapy (45.2%), traditional alternative medicine (42.0%), mind therapy (32.1%), and senses therapy (23.0%) (21). Yoga is a physical, mental, and spiritual discipline that originated in India. Yoga focuses on gentle stretching, exercises for breath control, and meditation.

The role of yoga in male infertility focuses on reducing anxiety and optimizing erectile function. To reduce stress and mental consequences of infertility, to improve semen parameters, to provide infertility counselling to a) Address root cause b) Improve mental health and c) Accept unfavorable outcomes (22).

Yoga, as a holistic science, has emerged as an effective method for both preventing and managing stress and its related disorders. It has been observed that yoga has an immediate calming effect on the body's response to stress by downregulating the HPA axis (23). Additionally, brief yoga-based relaxation training has been found to restore the function of the autonomic nervous system by balancing both sympathetic and parasympathetic indices towards a more normalized state (24). Research indicates that yoga reduces levels of salivary cortisol, as well as 24-hour urine levels of nor-epinephrine and epinephrine. These findings suggest that yoga can swiftly alleviate the body's response to stress. Although the exact mechanism of action remains unclear, it is hypothesized that certain yoga practices may promote dominance of the parasympathetic nervous system, possibly through direct stimulation of the vagus nerve (25). Regardless of the underlying physiological pathways, yoga has demonstrated immediate psychological benefits by reducing anxiety and enhancing feelings of emotional and spiritual well-being.

Simple lifestyle modifications like yoga-based lifestyle intervention (YBLI) are increasingly used alongside modern medicine to address complex medical conditions (26,27). However, the molecular mechanisms underlying the benefits of YBLI remain unknown. Since several modifiable lifestyle factors influence human sperm quality, studying the impact of YBLI could

aid infertile patients in adopting these techniques. Previous research by Dhawan demonstrated that YBLI intervention can regulate the sperm transcriptome (28). Another study involving chronically stressed women showed that YBLI can influence genome-wide DNA methylation patterns (29). Sperm DNA is highly vulnerable to genetic and epigenetic abnormalities due to its architecture (minimal cytosolic antioxidants and tight DNA packaging) (30). Our findings suggest that YBLI is linked with epigenetic changes in spermatozoa, with numerous loci experiencing alterations in DNA methylation status following yoga-based techniques. These epigenetic changes can directly affect gene expression levels, thereby regulating the physiological outcomes of YBLI. Yoga has been shown to elevate melatonin levels, a potent antioxidant primarily concentrated in mitochondria. This may lead to enhancements in mitochondrial integrity, which serve as both sources and targets of free radicals (27,28). Yoga practice might also enhance total antioxidant capacity in spermatozoa. Indeed, we observe reduced oxidative stress and improved DNA integrity in sperm following YBLI. Additionally, yoga leads to the upregulation of anti-inflammatory genes and downregulation of proinflammatory genes (31).

Yoga therapy also aids in enhancing circulation and supporting the proper functioning of internal organs. For men, practicing moola bandha has been linked to relieving spermatorrhea, preventing inguinal hernia, and regulating testosterone secretion. Moola bandha practice helps in heightening awareness of genital arousal sensations, potentially serving as a beneficial supplement for enhancing sexual desire and arousal. Moola bandha involves stretching the muscles of the pelvic floor, enhancing circulation in that region, and promoting balance, stimulation, and rejuvenation through techniques that heighten awareness and circulation. Consequently, incorporating exercises that incorporate moola bandha may be beneficial for individuals experiencing reduced sexual vitality and impaired sexual functioning. For men, practicing moola bandha has been linked to alleviating spermatorrhoea, preventing inguinal hernia, and regulating testosterone secretion (32). Additionally, as men age, their production of dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA), testosterone, and other androgens or sex hormones decreases. It's been observed that men's testosterone levels drop by about one percent for each year over the age of forty, with approximately 20% of men in their 60s experiencing significantly reduced testosterone levels. Since testosterone is pivotal for men's sexual functions, the age-related decline in its levels negatively impacts sexual performance (33). Yoga therapy aids in enhancing and integrating neuroendocrine axes, thereby improving

hormonal secretion and subsequently enhancing sexual desire and overall reproductive health (34).

Table: Yoga Module For Male Infertility – (35)

AGE RANGE	SPECIFIC YOGIC PRACTICE	RATIONALE
FOR YOUNG MEN	Kundalini Yoga, Moola Bandha, Weight-bearing Asanas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KY does not suppress sexual energy • MB causes pelvic floor muscle stretching • MB may also cause regulation of testosterone secretion
FOR MIDDLE-AGED MEN	Hatha Yoga practice, DRT and Pranayama	Maintaining good penile blood flow
FOR OLDER MALES	Kapalabhati, Ujjayi Pranayama, Yoga Mudra	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kapalabhati may maintain the growth of prostate • Yoga Mudra could be beneficial in preventing BPH

Conclusion:

This review suggests that while evidence for the direct impact of individual lifestyle or environmental factors on adult spermatogenesis is limited, prenatal exposures can significantly affect sperm production later in life. Changes in modern lifestyles, diets, and activity levels

likely have negative impacts on spermatogenesis, compounded by the adverse effects of sedentary behaviours and obesity. Environmental pollutants may further exacerbate these effects. Complementary and alternative medicine, such as yoga, may alleviate stress and anxiety, improve autonomic functions, and potentially enhance reproductive health. However, more focused scientific research is needed to understand the precise effects and mechanisms of yoga on male reproductive physiology. Overall, yoga shows promise in preventing infertility and promoting male reproductive health.

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